

AT-RISK LTO MIGRATION: A PRIORITISATION CASE STUDY

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Abstract – Ngā Taonga Sound and Vision is aspiring to become a digital archive – moving away from analogue materials and processes towards digital ones. As part of our digital preservation efforts, we have begun to apply a prioritisation model to digital materials stored on at-risk generations of LTO (referred to in this paper as Legacy LTO).

These LTO tapes range from generations 3-6 and are at risk due to format obsolescence and the possibility of tape failure. Some of the files are likely to be significant and unique, but others may either be insignificant or have been replaced by higher quality preservation files.

Ngā Taonga has recently developed a model for collection prioritisation to help inform our work, including preservation. We are now in the process of using this model to identify what percentage of the files on Legacy LTO are unique materials of high significance and access. This will help us make informed decisions about how to proceed with these items.

A case study was conducted with files on a sample set of our LTO3-LTO5 tapes. These files were analysed first with respect to the significance of their content and our ability to provide access to it and secondly, to understand the effects of file loss. We then considered a possible migration approach that combined these considerations.

The data gathered in this study has proven that our Legacy LTO tapes hold some unique files of high value alongside material that may not be worthy of migration. The results showed that applying a prioritisation lens in addition to an analysis of the impact of file loss could reduce the number of tapes we need to migrate.

This study will inform our migration plans. It also helps us to outline options for decision makers, including different levels of investment in migration based on impact of loss and value of content.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Migration from at-risk digital formats is a resource intensive undertaking. Ngā Taonga holds LTO3 to LTO6 tapes (referred to in this paper as Legacy LTO). The contents of these tapes need to be migrated to LTO9 to ensure their ongoing accessibility, usability, and care.

Perceptions of the value of this collection vary across the organisation, with some viewing the files as insignificant and redundant. Others see these materials as representing many hours of earlier digitisation and preservation work, and inclusive of unique born digital deposits. From working with this collection, we know that both views hold some truth.

We are currently operating in a fiscally restrained environment and recognise that the barriers to migration and their associated costs will only increase. The risk of losing content held on these legacy formats is high due to tape failure, proprietary software, and aging hardware. It is unlikely to be feasible or even desirable to migrate the entire collection.

Ngā Taonga has recently developed a model for prioritising work on collection items – both analogue and digital. The model considers the significance of the content, our ability to provide access to it, and the risk of loss of the material. These three considerations are combined to identify high priority items.

As part of our digital preservation efforts, we have begun to apply this model to the collections stored on at-risk (legacy) LTO. We believe that applying a prioritisation lens will reduce the number of files and tapes we need to migrate. This will allow us to create a business case for the migration work, and to use our resources to best effect.

This paper will outline the development of the collection on Legacy LTO and its associated risks, and present the fundamental principles of our prioritisation model, Hakune. It will then present a case study to illustrate how the model enables us to make informed decisions about our Legacy LTO materials.

II. DIGITAL COLLECTIONS AT NGĀ TAONGA

A. *The Collection*

Ngā Taonga Sound and Vision is responsible for collecting, caring for and sharing the audiovisual taonga (treasures) of New Zealand. The collection we care for includes nearly 840,000 titles, ranging from feature films to home movies, news broadcasts to milk advertisements. We hold materials such as nitrate and acetate film reels, video formats like U-matic and Betacam, audio formats such as lacquer disc and open reel tape, and an ever-increasing number of born digital deposits.

Ngā Taonga began as the Film Archive in 1981, later rebranding when the collection was significantly expanded with the acquisition of the Radio New Zealand Sound Archives (in 2012) and the TVNZ Archives (in 2014). In the last year we have added material from the Waitangi Tribunal and TV3 to the collection which will increase the number of titles by a further 50% (to over 1.2M). These collections contain a combination of analogue materials (some of which have been preserved to digital) and born digital materials.

B. *Preservation at Ngā Taonga*

The material realities of our audiovisual collection have led us to differentiate between a title that has been digitised and one that has been preserved to digital. In many collections, the motivator for digitising a collection item is to provide greater access and reduce physical handling. The digitised file supplements the original item but cannot be considered a replacement: both must be retained.

With audiovisual material, we endeavour to maintain the analogue original, however it is inevitable that eventually it will either degrade to the point where the content is lost, or we will be unable to run the equipment required to play it. Continued access to the content relies on a digital file.

For this reason, at Ngā Taonga we make a distinction between “digitised” and “preserved to digital.” Digitised means that a digital file exists for the title. Preserved to digital means that this file has been made from the best available source for the title and to a standard that meets our current preservation guidelines.

The Film Archive began to preserve to digital around 2008. Digitisation was happening at the same time, so files made in this period were not necessarily standardised in resolution or format. The types of digital files created range from high-quality film scans to off-air captures and digital access files.

In 2017 a Preservation Bundle structure was introduced as part of the standardisation of our preservation processes. The bundle structure formalises how preservation files are categorised and the folders they are stored in, keeping preservation master, original, and access files in one place.

Soon after, Ngā Taonga made the strategic decision to begin transitioning to a digital archive. This means moving away from analogue materials and ways of working towards digital ones, including providing high quality preservation files in digital formats.

In 2022, Ngā Taonga began a large-scale digitisation project, Utaina. This project is digitising nearly 340,000 magnetic media analogue items from the collection. We estimate that by the time Utaina is complete between 65-75% of titles will be considered preserved to digital.

C. *LTO Use at Ngā Taonga*

LTO or Linear Tape Open is a relatively long-term digital storage solution. As with all digital storage, migration is key to maintenance. This is not only because the tapes will wear out with use, but also to guard against obsolescence. There is zero to two generations of backwards compatibility between LTO generations, and each generation has doubled in storage capacity.

Ngā Taonga (as The Film Archive) began using LTO for digital collection storage in 2006. In its early years of digitisation, the archive used multiple LTO drives. During this time, different teams could be working with different generations of LTO tape depending on which drive they had access to.

When our transition to a digital archive began in earnest, Ngā Taonga was motivated to consider long term digital storage and access solutions. The Archive moved towards an on-premise tape library rather than the previous combination of on-disk and LTO storage.

At the outset of the Utaina project, our tape library housed 1 PB of data; we forecast 40-50 PB will be in use by the end of the project later this year. With help from Utaina funding, we upgraded our technology to a Scalar i6000 system with robotic solutions for automated digital retrieval. All LTO tapes within this system are LTO9, the latest generation until LTO10 was released a couple of months ago. LTO7s and LTO8s have been migrated to LTO9 and the bulk of our digital collection is stored within the Scalar and in this format.

D. Challenges with Our Legacy LTO

This study is primarily concerned with digital materials that pre-date the employment of our tape library. We have 4158 of these Legacy LTO tapes. The tapes are stored in temperature- and humidity-controlled environments with the masters housed at an offsite vault, and duplicates at one of our main facilities for ease of access.

Ngā Taonga had limited resources to invest in the initial setup of our LTO workflow, which led to an ad hoc process. There are three aspects to this: file creation, file naming and handling, and cataloguing. Each of these saw variation across teams and improved over time as digital expertise increased among kaimahi (staff). The changes in cataloguing practices have made it particularly difficult to get complete data on the number of files we have stored on LTO, their source and quality. We also encounter discrepancies between Collection Management System (CMS) data and LTO contents.

The current workflow for Legacy LTO file retrieval is time and resource intensive, relying on human labour and multiple systems to bridge the gap between current and legacy technologies. Continued access to this collection is complicated by

technological barriers, such as software and hardware obsolescence.

Ngā Taonga has 324 LTO3, 1062 LTO4, and 547 LTO5 tapes. The software used to read and restore from these tapes is proprietary, Mac OS based and capped at the Snow Leopard operating system. We are forced to maintain legacy machines and are unable to integrate these with our SAN (Storage Area Network) and automated LTO9 system due to both compatibility issues and security concerns.

Ngā Taonga has 177 LTO6 tapes which are also a concern, but these tapes were written with the opensource Linear Tape File System and so can be accessed via more modern hardware. For this reason, the LTO6 tapes have not been included in this study to date.

We can access our Legacy LTO through a combination of LTO5 and LTO6 drives due to the two generations of backwards compatibility for LTO1-7. However, LTO8 and 9 are only backwards compatible one generation, which means there is a substantial gap between these legacy tapes and our current LTO9 set-up that will need to be addressed.

The materials housed on Legacy LTO range from unique born digital deposits to deaccessioned files that are no longer considered part of the collection. In between are a variety of archive generated preservations and digitisations. Assessing which files to migrate and estimating the resources required to do so demands a robust prioritisation model.

III. HAKUNE: NGĀ TAONGA SOUND AND VISION'S PRIORITISATION MODEL

A. The Development of Hakune

The growth of our collection in recent years means that it is increasingly important that we use our resources to best effect. It is critical that we have a transparent, archive-wide system that we can use to help categorise collection material.

In 2024, Ngā Taonga developed a model that can be used to identify priority titles with respect to three different considerations:

- 1) *Tūhono (Access)* - our ability to share the title or collection.
- 2) *Tūhira (Significance)* - the significance of the content in the title or collection.
- 3) *Tūraru (Risk)* - the risk of loss of the content in the title or collection.

The model helps us make replicable, objective, and data driven decisions. The prioritisation model has been gifted the te reo Māori name “Hakune” which roughly translates to “be deliberate, careful, methodical.”

Hakune began with the goal to develop a system to prioritise materials in the collection for preservation to digital. We recognised that over half of our collection would be preserved to digital at the end of Utaina, and we needed to be targeted and deliberate with the remaining titles.

Many other organisations have preservation prioritisation systems, often consisting of two-dimensional matrices that balance significance vs risk. In some systems, an attempt is made to address audience connection, but this is often incorporated into the significance axis.

Increasing access to the collection is a key focus of the strategic vision for Ngā Taonga. Therefore, we felt our decision-making framework needed a more comprehensive way to consider our ability to provide access to material. We decided to explore whether the model could be expanded from a two-dimensional matrix to a three-dimensional one.

Hakune was developed through a co-design process that included consultation with kaimahi (staff) from across the archive, including the teams that most regularly deal with decisions regarding the collection.

We quickly realised a three-dimensional matrix could account for the overlapping (and sometimes incongruent) objectives of these teams when prioritising material. Each team can set the priorities within their own axis, but leadership determines how the organisational priorities overlay these. (For example, leadership might prioritise increasing access or mitigating risk.)

B. Key Considerations of Hakune

How a title is rated as high, medium or low for its axis depends on eight key considerations:

Tūhono (Access) must consider both the ease of rights clearance, and how likely it is that people will connect with the content. Additionally, it was important to prioritise content that would connect with iwi Māori (Māori kinship groups). Oftentimes material iwi Māori connect with cannot be shared publicly but it remains important to ensure iwi Māori are able to access it.

Tūraruru (Risk) must consider whether the format of the material has inherent risks that might make it likely to be unreadable in the short or medium term, the condition of the item (i.e. vinegar syndrome in film), and how many copies of the material we have in our collection.

Tūhira (Significance) must consider not only the significance of the material historically, socially and experientially (but the level of Mātauranga Māori (Māori knowledge) contained in the content.

Key considerations of Hakune

Figure 1: Key Considerations to rate items on the three axes Hakune—Ngā Taonga Sound and Vision’s prioritisation model

C. How to Use Hakune

Hakune considers how a title is categorised with respect to the key considerations to determine a rating of high, medium or low for Tūhira (Significance), Tūhono (Access), and Tūraru (Risk). The model uses the rating for each axis to sort our titles onto a 3D matrix with 27 cubes. Where a title sits on the matrix, informs decisions we might make about prioritisation for that title.

For example, our first priority for preservation to digital would be titles that have high significance that are also high risk and high access. In contrast, we might want to consider whether preservation to digital is merited for high-risk titles that hold foreign content that we cannot provide access to.

We are in the process of integrating the Hakune Key Consideration ratings into our CMS. This will enable us to search our CMS to find items of high access, significance or risk, or any combination of these depending on the priorities we set.

Although developed for preservation to digital, Hakune can help us prioritise collection materials for a wide range of archival activities. As part of widening the application for the model, we have chosen to integrate Hakune into our migration strategy for legacy digital formats.

IV. APPLYING HAKUNE PRIORITISATION TO LEGACY LTO MATERIAL

A. Pre-study Thinking/ Hypothesis

The state of thinking about the Legacy LTO collection prior to this case-study was along a spectrum. At one end, people believed that nothing on these tapes would be high value, and that most of the files were redundant (i.e. replaced by new preservation files). On the other end, people worried that many of the files were unique and therefore we should be working to migrate everything on the tapes as soon as possible.

The purpose of this study was to test our hypothesis that applying Hakune to the Legacy LTO collection would reduce the number of files or tapes we needed to migrate. A secondary hypothesis was that having more data about the content that we hold on Legacy LTO would help us make educated decisions about digital preservation and a case for migration.

B. The Dataset

The study presented here considers a sample set of LTO tapes from our LTO3-5 generations. Hakune exists as a complete framework, but ratings have not yet been incorporated into our CMS. Instead, we have applied the criteria of the model by exporting CMS data and evaluating it through Microsoft Excel. We chose to initially apply the model to a subset of tapes to test the concept before attempting to map the entire collection because of the time-consuming nature of evaluating multiple criteria in Excel and the complexity of the data surrounding the LTO collection.

We began by identifying 180 tapes to work with; this is just under ten percent of the Legacy LTO3-5 tapes (around 1934, excluding duplicates). Upon auditing the tapes within the collection, we found that the majority are LTO4 followed by LTO5. With this in mind, we have split the sample set between generations as follows: 46 LTO3, 67 LTO4, and 67 LTO5.

Rather than selecting the tapes at complete random, we skewed the sample set to ensure that it includes tapes that are known to hold materials that do not have an analogue equivalent. This ensures that we will catch some “worst case scenario” examples in our sample set.

C. The Approach

The main considerations for our decision making were the impact of file loss and the value of the content according to Hakune prioritisation. Therefore, we needed to gather data on where the files stored on Legacy LTO sat with respect to these considerations.

1) Impact of File Loss

Even before the proliferation of digital, audiovisual collections were concerned with duplication. A news segment shot on film might be transferred to a video format for broadcast, and then an ex-air version might be recorded by the station, including onscreen graphics and anchor segments. A feature film would generally have a negative, a positive, and a print. Today, both these examples will likely also have a digital version of some type.

Because of this complexity, CMS data at Ngā Taonga is structured by title and material. The news segment or feature film is recorded as the title with information about things like content, production

company, credits, or date aired. The reels and/or tapes that hold that content are recorded as materials, with details like video format, reel length, or file size. One title will generally have more than one material record attached.

The Tūraru (Risk) axis rating is clearly high for files that are unique (i.e.: only exist on Legacy LTO) but we also wanted to consider some moderate risk titles. These are titles that have limited copies or where we could save duplication of preservation efforts by retrieving an existing file off Legacy LTO rather than re-preserving the item from an analogue source.

We have agreed upon a series of ratings to determine the impact of file loss, which we think will be helpful for digital preservation decision making.

These file loss ratings can be simplified into five categories in terms of analysing files on Legacy LTO:

- Unique: Content that will be lost forever if we do not migrate the files.
- Might be highest quality: The LTO file might be the highest quality we could ever hold.
- Saves us work: Migrating the LTO file saves us work re-preserving analogue items.
- Might be usable: Migrating the LTO file might find additional existing preservation files.
- Redundant: The file on LTO is redundant.

2) Hakune Prioritisation

When it came to investigating the content on Legacy LTO, we applied the model the same way we would for prioritising preservation to digital for analogue materials. Our highest priority is items that rank highly on all three axes.

We know that many of these files are high risk for Tūraru, but we also needed to use the title records to ascertain where things fall on the Tūhono (Access) and Tūhira (Significance) axes of Hakune. We used title information like date created, production company, credits, and keywords to find files that rate highly against set criteria for these axes. We agreed to only focus on the criteria that would result in a high rating for these axes.

Using CMS data exported to Excel, we have applied each criterion to the title record data to get a result of high, not high, unknown, or excluded. Unknown is returned when we do not have the data required to make an assessment on a certain criterion. Excluded files are those that have been

deaccessioned as well as those excluded by certain criteria (i.e. foreign titles). The results for Tūhono (Access) and Tūhira (Significance) were then combined so that each title has a ranking based on its results in each axis.

Hakune prioritisation rankings can be simplified into five categories in terms of analysing files on Legacy LTO:

- Priority 1: Files *known to be* high significance and access.
- Priority 2: Files *known to be* high significance and files *known to be* high access that *might be* high significance.
- Priority 3: Files that *might be* high significance, including those *not known to be* high access.
- Not a migration priority: Files that are *not known to be* high significance.

3) Combined Approach

There are numerous ways we could use a combination of the data gathered regarding impact of file loss and Hakune prioritisation to help us establish a migration approach. At one extreme, we could choose to only migrate files that would be lost forever and are known to have content of high Tūhira (Significance) and Tūhono (Access). However, we recognised that the data about this collection is incomplete in many instances, and that we have already invested a lot of resources in the creation of these files.

For the purposes of this study, we chose a comprehensive, but pragmatic combined approach that acknowledges the past efforts put into creating the files stored on Legacy LTO while also considering the value of the content of those files.

This combined approach was to:

- 1) Migrate all unique files if they are priority 1-3 (content is *known to be* or *might be* high significance).
- 2) Migrate files that might be the highest quality if they are priority 1 or 2 (content that is *known to be* high significance or *known to be* high access *and might be* high significance).
- 3) Migrate files that could save us work re-preserving analogue items if they are priority 1 (content that is *known to be* high significance *and* high access).

Impact of File Loss vs Hakune for different generation sample sets

	LTO 3	LTO 4	LTO 5	All
# of tapes in study	46	67	67	180
# of files in study (less excluded files)	2164	5277	6612	14053

	LTO 3	LTO 4	LTO 5	All
Files to be migrated considering Hakune	50%	35%	69%	53%
To be migrated not considering Hakune	92%	85%	89%	88%
Percent reduction	45%	59%	22%	39%

	Priority 1				Priority 2				Priority 3				Not a migration priority				Totals			
Unique	4.1%	0.8%	0.3%	1.1%	22.5%	4.1%	8.8%	9.1%	22.1%	14.1%	52.0%	33.2%	31.0%	1.6%	0.1%	5.4%	79.7%	20.6%	61.2%	48.8%
High Quality	0.4%	3.4%	1.2%	1.9%	1.3%	6.1%	4.6%	4.7%	5.2%	5.9%	3.6%	4.7%	1.8%	3.1%	0.2%	1.6%	8.8%	18.5%	9.7%	12.9%
Saves us work	0.0%	6.3%	2.2%	3.4%	2.0%	9.3%	2.1%	4.8%	0.7%	28.3%	13.0%	16.8%	1.0%	1.5%	0.4%	0.9%	3.7%	45.4%	17.7%	25.9%
Might be usable	0.5%	0.6%	0.5%	0.5%	1.1%	1.1%	1.6%	1.4%	0.3%	3.8%	2.4%	2.6%	1.5%	3.4%	0.3%	1.7%	3.4%	8.9%	4.8%	6.1%
Redundant	0.6%	0.9%	0.5%	0.7%	2.8%	3.5%	2.9%	3.1%	0.4%	1.5%	2.9%	2.0%	0.6%	0.6%	0.2%	0.4%	4.4%	6.6%	6.6%	6.3%
Total	5.7%	12.0%	4.7%	7.6%	29.7%	24.2%	20.1%	23.1%	28.7%	53.5%	74.0%	59.4%	35.9%	10.3%	1.2%	10.0%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 1: LTO3-5 Files (% sample set)- Impact of File Loss Rating vs Hakune Rating

Figure 2: % of Files to be migrated (blue) by LTO tape (LTO3 Sample set)

Figure 3: % of Files to be migrated (blue) by LTO tape (LTO4 Sample set)

Figure 4: % of Files to be migrated (blue) by LTO tape (LTO5 Sample set)

D. Analysis

We analysed the Legacy LTO collection at both file and tape level. This means we gathered aggregate data about the number of files that met our criteria and also kept track of which tapes these files were on. This was done with the understanding that we might restore at a tape level rather than a file level. In other words, once we decided to restore a tape, we would migrate all the materials on that tape, rather than just the files we had identified as high value.

As of submission of this paper, we have completed our analysis of the sample sets of LTO3-5 tapes. These tapes hold a total of 14,149 files.

96 of these files have been excluded either because they are foreign titles or deaccessioned files. These files have been omitted from the following results.

V. FINDINGS

At a file level, the data from our analysis clearly showed that the materials on the tapes analysed did not land at either end of the spectrum of current thinking.

- A significant portion of the files are known to be high significance or access.
 - At least 20% of the files across the LTO 3-5 subsets are known to be high significance or access (Priority 1 and 2). If we include all of those that might be high in these axes (Priority 3), that could be up to 53%.
- Not many of the files are redundant.
 - Just over 6% of the files across the LTO3-5 subsets are redundant and 32% would require duplication of resources (i.e. re-preservation work) to replace.

However;

- Not all of the files rank highly on Hakune.
 - 10% of the files on our Legacy LTO tapes are not known to be high significance (not Priority 1-3).
- The files are not all unique.
 - Around 51% of files could be recreated or sourced from elsewhere. However, in 13% of instances this might result in a lower quality file than what we hold on LTO.

The combined analysis has confirmed that:

- 1) *There is unique material on Legacy LTO that will be high significance and/or access.*
- 2) *There are some files that might be the best digital file we could ever hold.*
- 3) *We can ensure we have used our resources to best effect by migrating some files which save us re-preserving analogue items.*

Applying this combined lens reduces the number of files that need to be migrated from almost 88% down to 53% across the full data set, a reduction of around 40%.

Among our sample sets, LTO4 tapes saw the greatest benefit by applying Hakune, with a 59% reduction in the number of files to be migrated, and LTO5 saw the least at 22%. This variation in effectiveness can be explained by a lack of cataloguing information for many titles recorded by off-air capture and an increase in the presence of such files on LTO5. This is discussed in more detail further on in this paper.

There is no direct correlation between the number of files to be migrated and the amount of effort involved in migration at a tape level. This is due to the huge variation in number of files per tape across this subset, which ranges from 1 to 1301.

Applying the combined analysis to the dataset allows us to propose non-migration for 20 tapes. While this only results in a decrease of approximately 10% of the tapes, it is worth reconsidering migration at a tape level. It might be better to recommend a threshold at which we would only migrate individual files on a tape. This would not save us effort in restoring the tape but would save considerable effort in file processing.

It is worth reiterating that our sample set was skewed towards titles where we hold only digital materials. This ensured that we would be able to see the worst-case scenario and means we will likely see a more savings in migration effort when applied across all tapes.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A. Areas for Improvement

As expected, the findings show that applying a prioritisation lens to the migration of Legacy LTO material can help to reduce the scale of migration

required. However, the case study also highlighted a number of challenges which are areas for improvement as we continue to develop our Legacy LTO migration strategy.

1) *Incorporating Hakune into our CMS*

We have plans to include the Hakune Key Consideration ratings of titles in our CMS data, but this has not been incorporated yet. This meant that we needed to export the data to an external program (Excel) and apply a complex system to parse it. This required working with subsets of data and developing a system of multiple sheets and formulas to establish the findings. The process was cumbersome, frustrating, and prone to human error.

The procedure for identifying which items ranked high for Tūhira (Significance) and Tūhono (Access) would be streamlined if it were able to be done in the CMS. The Archive is currently in the process of adopting a new CMS system and there are plans to incorporate Hakune into that system to improve our ability to search based on the prioritisation model.

2) *Data Cleaning*

For the best and most reliable results, Hakune requires trustworthy and complete data about the collection. We have a lot of passionate people working across the organisation to clean and improve the data in our CMS, but there are and will continue to be areas where we just do not have the information we need about a particular title or material to confidently map it to the axes. We are continuing to refine how we search for high priority items, and this will aid the analysis of our Legacy LTO.

There are plans to perform some data cleaning as part of the migration to our new CMS system, but it will be important to continue to work to improve the quality of our data. Part of this is tracking the level of confidence we have in a particular title's rating on Hakune by noting the method by which that rating was assigned (i.e. a rating based off data searches vs an archivist review of the title).

3) *Off-Air Captures.*

Off-Air captures contribute significantly to the number of titles that cannot be confidently mapped to Hakune axes. These are programmes recorded from broadcast television to VHS, DVD, or as digital files using consumer-grade equipment. As a result,

the recordings are low quality but include extra context, such as ad breaks and newsroom footage that are not always available in the broadcast versions of the titles.

Off-Airs accounted for a considerable amount of our collecting in the early-to-mid 2000s and make up a high percentage of the files in this subset, especially those held only on LTO5. Recordings were either made of individual programmes or harvested from a specific channel on a specific date. In the latter instances, we sometimes lack information about which programmes were captured. In both cases, cataloguing of Off-Air captures was scant, with some fields left entirely blank. The lack of item-level data means that most Off-Air captures are falling into the 'might be high significance' category simply because the data we have about them is incomplete. The evolution of our archive, particularly with the addition of TVNZ and TV3 programming into the collection means that some of this content might be redundant.

We would recommend making further decisions about the significance of Off-Air captures (based on information like channel and date) which could result in a lower prioritisation rating for some of these titles.

4) *Ownership*

Responsibility for collections on Legacy LTO has bounced around teams between Born Digital, Preservation, and ICT. Different teams have researched this collection and how we might better care for it, but it has not been core to any one team's work and so has tended to take a back seat to other priorities.

In crafting a migration strategy, it will be important to define a clear area of ownership for these materials moving forward. One possibility is our newly established Digital Delivery team, which has led the work involved in this case study.

B. Summary

Applying the Hakune prioritisation model to files stored on Legacy LTO has given us new data-driven insights into the value of these materials. We can now confidently say that rather than being largely redundant and low value or largely unique and high value, this collection sits somewhere in the middle.

Identifying the high priority titles and creating a breakdown of the impact of file loss will allow us to better scope migration plans for this collection.

The data we have gathered will allow us to outline options for decision makers. This will include capturing different levels of investment in migration based on impact of loss and value of content.

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Lara Simmons is the Lead Advisor Collection Management for Ngā Taonga Sound and Vision. She led the project to develop the prioritisation model, Hakune. Her career history includes years spent as a structural engineer before receiving her Masters of Museum and Heritage Practice where she transitioned to archival work.

